

(General Announcement) What is the Community Connections series?

It is a quarterly virtual gathering for RADx-UP focused organizations to network, collaborate, and learn from other organizations around the U.S, territories and Tribal Nations.

Community partners rotate leading the quarterly gathering with the support of the CDCC Community Engagement Team.

Why does Community Connections exist?

- ❖ To create an informal space to engage and connect with community partners
- ❖ To facilitate thought provoking presentations and discussions
- ❖ To exchange best practices, resources, and ideas
- ❖ To bring awareness to the amazing work we do in our communities

Interested in seeing past Community Connections programs? Check out our webpage here (link)!

Join us in YEAR on Date 1, Date 2, Date 3, Date 4

Open for Nominations (or call for nominations are now open):

Community Connections (and the CDCC?) is seeking community partners (CPs) that are doing amazing things in their RADxUP projects and in their communities! If you are RADxUP affiliated as CDCC staff, a funded project, or as a community organization/partner, this is your opportunity to nominate a CP to share!

The nomination process is easy. Simply send Alex James an email at [email] an email with the name and contact information of the community partner or organization you would like to nominate!

Interested in learning more about Community Connections? Check out our webpage and send us an email if you would like to be featured on the page!